

Mixing Importance Performance, Swot and Balanced Scorecard Analysis to Develop Strategic Plan at Astrini Hospital Wonogiri

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Know what customer need in healthcare service is one of important thing for hospital to win competition in competitive era. Importance performance analysis is a method which is show us about two-dimension, importance and performance. IPA tool, it helps hospital leaders and managers to see about their hospital situation and it helps hospital management to analyze about strength and weakness point their hospital and make balance scorecard to achieve hospital strategic plan appropriately.

Purpose: To see about using IPA tool and mix it with SWOT and balanced scorecard in develop strategic plan policy at Astrini Hospital Wonogiri

Method: we measuring IPA with servperf model five-dimension, tangible, responsiveness, reliability, empathy and safety. Sample of measurement are inpatient patient at Astrini Hospital (25 – 55 years old), and total respondent are fifteen people (n=15), SWOT and Balanced scorecard analysis use in focused group discussion from hospital management based on IPA measurement.

Result and discussion: we get four of five dimensions are good and patient is satisfied with hospital performance overall. Tangible dimension is only one with low point (-0,2) and it mean our patient not satisfied with hospital performance. Each dimension, it has some question and it can be hospital leader and manager consideration during analyze SWOT (strength, weakness, opportunity, and threat) & BSC (balanced score card) to develop a hospital strategic plan.

Conclusion: Hospital management is must to know what their patient need and want when they come to hospital to seek medical service. Using IPA, and then mix its with SWOT and balanced scorecard can be consideration for hospital management to analyze existing condition and then analyze hospital strategic plan further. Directly scoring from hospital patient, it can be an indicator is the hospital already give them appropriate medical service what they need and expect from hospital.

KEYWORD: Importance performance analysis, Strategic plan, Servperf model

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INTRODUCTION

Know what customer need and expectation for hospital medical services is one of important thing that all of hospital leaders or manager must be realize. Higher medical service that patient receives form healthcare facilities or healthcare professional, It will correlated with patient satisfaction. This sentence is easy to say, but it will not really easy to implemented at field.

IPA (Importance performance analysis is a method that it shows us about two dimensions, there are performance and importance. Performance presented that what customer / patient receive when they seek a service from organization. Importance itself is what customer think it must be done by organization.

Picture 1. IPA Quadrant Coordinate

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Picture 1 show us there are four quadrants at IPA tool with different means for each quadrant. Quadrant A, show us that is important for customers, but they didn't receive what they expect from organization. Quadrant A is the most urgent thing to be improve for organization.

Quadrant B, it shows important to customer and organization can be delivered what customer expect from them. It must go on for further. Quadrant C, it shows not really important for customer and organization cannot delivered their service to customer well. Its low priority to improve. Quadrant D, it shows not important for customer but organization performance is well.

With this IPA tool, it helps hospital leaders and manager to see their hospital existing service level, so they can be make an appropriate strategic for their hospital based on IPA score and mix it with SWOT and Balanced scorecard analysis.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

At 1977, Martilla and James create a method its called by importance performance analysis, and now it common method used in organization management to develop an optimal organization performance.

IPA is a method that show us about performance (organization) dimension (horizontal axis) and then importance (customer) dimension (vertical axis). Quality from organization or company is very important to make it competitive in market. One of the important step is know what our customer needed and expect from us and then evaluate it if we didn't make it. Delivered a high quality service can be make our organization efficient, improve market share, improve profit and then we can deliver a high quality service.

Measuring service quality is a strategic step for hospital leaders or managers to improve their hospital performance higher and higher. Strategic plan is one of popular organization management use for achieve their goals. Strategic plan need some analysis like example from organization vision, mission, value and it culture, and then we must see form internal / external factor (SWOT). After that we going to choose priority with balanced scorecard.

METHOD

We measuring IPA with servperf model from Domanhour and Bourie, which is it has 27 questions must be answered by respondent. Sample respondent are 15-person (30%) form total inpatient population, and they are 25 – 55 years old. Score criteria is like:

Score	Importance	peformance
1	Very unimportant	Very dissatisfied
2	unimportant	Dissatisfied
3	Quiet important	Quite Satisfied

4	important	Satisfied
5	Very important	Very satisfied

And for questioner, there are 27 point that must be answered by respondent:

Table 1. Servperf model (Domanhour & Bourie)

No	Question
1	Hospital design is easy to access services.
2	Every unit at hospital quickly helps.
3	Hospital facilities and waiting room is comfortable.
4	Hospital has modern technologies medical equipment.
5	Hospital personnel wear uniform appropriate.
6	Easy to locate hospital.
7	Outpatient clinic is clean and comfortable.
8	Hospital staff give me appropriate service and on-time
9	Hospital staff helps to solve my problem
10	Hospital service offer is according what i heard before
11	Medical specialist what I need is available in hospital
12	I trust hospital staff
13	Hospital staff quickly response my query
14	Hospital staff know what I needed
15	My medical document is done accurately
16	I feel safe when hospital staff come to me
17	Hospital staff has a knowledge to answer my question and problem
18	Hospital staff always ready to work with me
19	Medical service is informed by hospital to me when it will be done
20	Hospital staff has a good attitude
21	Hospital staff routinely observe my health problem
22	Patient information is confidential
23	Hospital staff very helpful to me
24	Inpatient interest is always be priority
25	Medical team is good attitude and fun
26	Work and time allocate appropriately for inpatient
27	Hospital staff know what I needed for my health

RESULT

From servperf questioner, we get the result is :
Tangible, n = 15, atributte= 7

Table 2. Tangible Dimension

Tangible	x (performance)	y (importance)	x-y
1	4.1	4.5	-0.4

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2	4.5	4.7	-0.2
3	4.3	4.3	0.0
4	4.3	4.7	-0.4
5	4.7	4.8	-0.1
6	4.7	4.6	0.1
7	4.4	4.7	-0.3
Σ	31.0	32.3	-1.3
atribut	7	7	7
mean	4.4	4.6	-0.2

Table 4. Reliability dimension

Reliability	X (performance)	y (importance)	x-y
8	4.7	4.7	0
9	4.7	4.7	0
10	4.6	4.6	0
11	4.9	4.7	0.2
Σ	18.9	18.7	0.2
atribut	4	4	4
mean	4.7	4.7	0.1

Picture 2. Tangible Coordinate

Picture 3. Reliability coordinate

Table 3. Tangible Dimension Analyze

Customer Satisfaction	At Tangible dimension, inpatient at Astrini hospital feel unsatisfied ($x-y = -0.2$ $x-y < 0$ (dissatisfaction)
Quadrant A	Attribute 4 " Hospital has modern technologies medical equipment, need priority to improve
Quadrant B	Attribute 2" Hospital staff quickly response", and attribute 5 "Hospital personnel wear uniform appropriately" need go on for further
Quadrant C	Attribute 1 " Hospital design is easy to access services." And attribute 3 " Hospital facilities and waiting room is comfortable." Low priority for improvement
Quadrant D	-

Reliability, n = 15, attribute = 4

Table 5. Reliability dimension analysis

Customer Satisfied	Reliability dimension overall is going well based on ($x-y = 0.1$ $x-y > 0$ (excellent)
Quadrant A	-
Quadrant B	Attribute 11" Medical specialist what I need is available in hospital", is must going on for furthermore
Quadrant C	Atribut 10 " Hospital service offer is according what I heard before" Low priority to improvement
Quadrant D	-

Empathy, n = 15, atribut = 4

Table 6. Empathy dimension

Empathy	x (performance)	y (importance)	x-y
12	4.7	4.7	0
13	4.8	4.7	0.1
14	4.9	4.7	0.2
15	4.4	4.5	-0.1

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Σ	18.8	18.6	0.2
atribut	4	4	4
mean	4.7	4.7	0.05

Picture 4. Empathy coordinate

Table 7. Empathy dimension Analysis

Customer Satisfaction	Empathy dimension overall is going well based on $(x-y) = 0.1$ $x-y > 0$ (excellent)
Quadrant A	-
Quadrant B	Attribute 13 "Hospital staff quickly response my query", and attribute 14 "Hospital staff know what I needed" is must going on furthermore
Quadrant C	Attribute 15 "My medical document is done accurately" Low priority to improvement
Quadrant D	-

Safety, n = 15, attribute = 4

Table 8. Safety dimension

Safety	x (performance)	y (Importance)	x-y
16	4.6	4.7	-0.1
17	4.7	4.7	0
18	4.5	4.6	-0.1
19	4.7	4.5	0.2
Σ	18.5	18.5	0
atribut	4	4	4
mean	4.6	4.6	0.0

Picture 5. Safety coordinate

Table 9. Safety dimension analysis

Customes Satisfaction	Safety dimension overall is going well based on $(x-y) = 0$ $x-y = 0$ (satisfaction)
Quadrant A	attribute 16 "I feel safe when hospital staff come to me" Attribute 18 "Hospital staff always ready to work with me" high priority to make improvement here
Quadrant B	Attribute 17 "Hospital staff has a knowledge to answer my question and problem", must going on furthermore
Quadrant C	-
Quadrant D	-

Responsiveness, n = 15, attribute = 8

Tabel 10. Responsiveness dimension

Responsive	x (performance)	y (Importance)	x-y
20	4.8	4.7	0.1
21	4.7	4.7	0
22	4.6	4.7	-0.1
23	4.6	4.7	-0.1
24	4.7	4.5	0.2
25	4.7	4.7	0
26	4.7	4.7	0
27	4.9	4.7	0.2
Σ	37.7	37.4	0.3
atribut	8	8	8
mean	4.7	4.7	0.0

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Picture 6. Responsiveness coordinate

Table 11. Responsiveness dimension analysis

Customer satisfaction	Responsiveness dimension overall is going well based on $(x-y) = 0$ $x-y = 0$ (satisfaction)
Quadrant A	attribute 23 " Hospital staff very helpful to me" high priority to improvement
Quadrant B	Attribute 20 " Hospital staff has a good attitude" dan attribute 27 " Hospital staff know what I needed for my health", must going on furthermore
Quadrant C	Attribute 24 " Inpatient interest is always be priority" low priority
Quadrant D	-

From 5 servperf dimension we measured by questioner to 15 patients at ward, it shows that tangible dimension is the only one that patients are unsatisfied. Reliability, empathy, responsiveness dan safety dimension are dimension which is patients satisfied with hospital performance.

Beside 5 dimension what we mentioned it before, there are some point that high priority need improve for better services, it likes modern technologies medical equipment, patient safety feels when they contact with healthcare professional and hospital staff helpful.

With data from IPA measurement, we are going to input that data to SWOT analysis and balanced scorecard. This is SWOT analysis and balanced scorecard based on IPA and discussion from hospital management:

INTERNAL FACTOR

Strength

Table 12. Strength

No	Factor	Var	Score	Total
1	Patient Loyalty	0.2	8	1.6
2	Priority service orthopedic and pediatric	0.2	8	1.6
3	Organization structur	0.2	7	1.4
4	Accreditation	0.2	8	1.6
5	High quality third party	0.2	7	1.4
6	Staff empowered	0.2	7	1.4
Total				9

Weakness

Table 13. Weakness analysis

No	Factor	Var	Score	Total
1	Hospital space is limit	0.2	9	1.8
2	Parking area is limited	0.2	8	1.6
3	Hospital medical equipment	0.2	7	1.4
4	Outpatient still majority at afternoon time	0.2	7	1.4
5	Staff attitude still need improvement	0.2	9	1.8
6	IT technologies still underperform	0.2	7	1.4
Total				9.4

External factor

Opportunities

Table 14. Opportunities analysis

No	Factor	Var	Score	Total
1	There are lot of citizen community	0.2	7	1.4

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2	Hospital located at main road	0.2	8	1.6
3	Hospital located at civil house	0.2	8	1.6
4	Good relation with external such as regulators	0.2	7	1.4
5	Already has contract service with UHC national	0.2	9	1.8
Total				7.8

Picture 7. SWOT Graphic

Threats

Table 15. Threats analysis

No	Factor	Var	Score	Total
1	There are some hospital within 5 KM	0.2	8	1.6
2	Regulation change quickly	0.2	8	1.6
3	Inflation	0.2	7	1.4
4	No significant improvement for UHC cost	0.2	6	1.2
5	Competitive fee for medical specialist	0.2	8	1.6
Total				7.4

After we done with analysis, so we go to SWOT coordinate to make a decision what strategy we need. Bellow is the result of SWOT analysis coordinate and table.

Picture 7 indicate that Astrini Hospital position at quadrant 1 and 2. In this quadrant we need diversification and aggressive strategy. We decided that we must has an innovation service that patient no longer must come to hospital, and we need aggressive strategic such as marketing division to improve our hospital capital.

After we done with our strategy (diversification and aggressive) we make some priority improvement for our hospital. There are 4 area that must improve rapidly:

1. Personnel and organization
2. Internal business
3. Financial
4. Stakeholders

At Personnel and organization, our focus is to improve personnel competency, improve our facilities, improve hospital technologies information, and improve work culture.

At internal business we focus on GCG and priority – quality service. We focus on capital gain and efficient budget. Then the last one is we are going to satisfied our stakeholders such as patient, hospital owner, shareholders and etc.

After we perform this method to develop our hospital strategy plan, there is some positive trend especially in capital grow. We made 15 – 20% capital gain higher each month if we compare with capital at 2022 each month.

CONCLUSION

Hospital management must realize what their customer need and expect form hospital service if we want our hospital still competitive in market share. Using IPA, can be consideration for hospital management to make analysis based on what patient expect from them, and make a better input for SWOT analysis. Direct opinion and input from customer is important indicator that show us about is our hospital already give our customer appropriate service or not.

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